

Influence of counterions on the aggregation of ionic surfactants and the Corrin-Harkins equation[†]

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The Corrin-Harkins equation provides a convenient experimental method for determining the counterion binding constants of ionic surfactants and in this review paper the suitability of this method has been assessed using various surfactant + salt systems. The criteria for the successful application of this method are: (i) the chosen ionic surfactant + salt system must contain single counterion, (ii) the aggregation number and the number of counterions bound per micelle must increase proportionately with increase in the salt concentration (c_e), and (iii) as c_e increases, the extent of decrease in the critical micelle concentration (cmc) must be such that the value of the sum $cmc + c_e$ must also increase. If the ionic surfactant + salt system contains two counterions, then the Corrin-Harkins equation takes a modified form, which is called the modified Corrin-Harkins equation. A sudden shift in the value of the slope of the Corrin-Harkins or modified Corrin-Harkins equation is indicative of a shape change of ionic micelle. In the case of ionic surfactant + salt system containing two counterions, the non-linearity of the modified Corrin-Harkins plot may be utilized to estimate the selectivity coefficient for the exchange of ions at the micellar surface.

Keywords: Corrin-Harkins equation, counterion binding constant, modified Corrin-Harkins equation, micellar shape change, selectivity coefficient.

Introduction

Surfactant molecules consist of hydrophobic and hydrophilic portions due to which they possess the amphiphilic character, viz. hydrophobicity and hydrophilicity. The balance between hydrophilicity and hydrophobicity is very crucial for a molecule to behave as a surfactant. Surfactants exhibit amphiphilic behaviour in solvents other than water also and therefore, in general, solvophobicity and solvophilicity terms are used to represent the dual character of surfactants.

Phospholipids, fatty acids and bile salts are some of the examples of naturally occurring surfactants, which are classified as bio-surfactants. Surfactants used for domestic and industrial purposes are mostly synthetic. Bio-surfactants and synthetic surfactants are classified further as anionic, cationic, nonionic and zwitterionic. Surfactants may contain single-chain or double-chain or even triple-chain hydrocarbon tails. Surfactant molecules containing two head groups and two hydrocarbon chains have also been synthesized.

Such surfactants are called gemini (or dimeric) surfactants if the spacer is between the two head groups or bolaforms if the spacer is between the hydrocarbon chains. Surfactants containing one or more fluorinated or partially fluorinated hydrophobic groups are known as fluorosurfactants. Metallosurfactants are another class of surfactants in which the surfactant molecule contains a coordination metal complex as an integral structural component.

Surfactants exhibit two very important properties on account of their amphiphilic character, viz. surface activity and self-organisation. Due to surface activity, surfactants adsorb at interfaces thereby lowering the surface tension of a solution and form monolayer, film and multilayers. Due to self-organisation, surfactants form aggregates like micelles, vesicles and membranes. Self-organization or aggregation of a surfactant in solution is commonly called as micellization and hydrophobic interaction is considered to be responsible for this. Water molecules become more ordered around the

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hydrocarbon tail of a surfactant. Transfer of hydrophobic tails of a surfactant from bulk water into micellar phase results in positive entropy change due to disordering of the ordered water molecules around the hydrocarbon tail. The entropy generated thus in the solvent medium drives the micellization process and hence micellization is a solvent induced phenomenon. Micellization of surfactants in solution always begins at a particular critical concentration known as the critical micelle concentration (cmc). Below the cmc, adsorption of surfactant monomers at the air-solution interface is the predominant phenomenon.

In ionic surfactants, repulsive interaction between the head groups tends to oppose the micellization process. Binding of counterions to an ionic micelle, on the other hand, screens the repulsive interaction between the head groups thereby favouring the micellization process. Counterions thus play significant role in micellization of ionic surfactants and counterion binding constant is considered to be an important parameter in the assessment of micellization phenomenon. Therefore, investigating the counterion binding behaviour of various surfactants in the presence of different counterions has been one of the aspects of research in the field of surfactant chemistry¹⁻⁴². The counterion binding constant (β) is defined as the ratio of the number of counterions bound to a micelle to the number of surfactant monomers present in an ionic micelle (aggregation number). The most commonly used practical methods for the determination of counterion binding constant are the Corrin-Harkins (CH) method^{1,42-45} and the slope-ratio method^{42,46,47}. During application of the CH method for determining β in various types of ionic surfactant + salt systems, we obtained some new results. Those results reported elsewhere⁴⁸⁻⁵⁷ are reviewed in this paper. Since our discussion in this paper is limited to the CH method, this method is described in the next section.

The Corrin-Harkins method

In this method, β is determined by using the CH equation^{1,2,42-44} written generally as

$$\ln c_0 = A - \beta \ln c_c \quad (1)$$

In eq. (1) c_0 and c_c represent cmc and total concentration of the counterion in the solution, respectively. The term A is equated to $\Delta G_m^0/(RT)$, where ΔG_m^0 is the standard Gibbs free energy of micellization per mole of surfactant monomer,

R is the gas constant and T is absolute temperature. Eq. (1) is derived by considering equilibrium between ionic micelles, surfactant monomeric ions and counterions, by assuming micelles to be monodispersed, and then by applying the thermodynamic criterion in terms of Gibbs free energy for the equilibrium^{1,2,42-44}. Generally concentrations are used in eq. (1) in place of activity terms because the concentrations involved are not in the too high range, otherwise activities are evaluated by applying the Debye-Hückel equation. In the presence of added electrolyte, eq. (1) is written more explicitly as

$$\ln c_0 = A - \beta \ln (pc_0 + qc_e) \quad (2)$$

where c_e is the concentration of the added electrolyte. The values of p and q in eq. (2) depend upon the type of ionic surfactant and salt. For e.g. if ionic surfactant and electrolyte are of 1:1 type, then $p = q = 1$ and in the case of a cationic gemini surfactant $p = 2$. The β term is represented as $\beta = m/n$, where m is the number of counterions bound to a micelle and n is the aggregation number. The CH eq. (2) provides a basis for the experimental determination of β and in this method cmc of an ionic surfactant is measured as a function of concentration of added electrolyte. Deviation from the CH equation was reported at high electrolyte concentration which was attributed to salting-out effect^{2,3,58-61}. In this review, we mainly discuss the deviations from the CH equation reported⁴⁸⁻⁵⁷ in ionic surfactant + salt systems containing not so high concentration of salt.

Aqueous surfactant + salt system with single counterion

The representative CH plots for sodium dodecylsulfate (SDS)⁵¹, cetylpyridinium chloride (CPC)⁴⁹ and sodium deoxycholate (SDC)⁶² in the presence of sodium chloride in aqueous medium are shown in Fig. 1. Since the CH plots are linear, the values of β are obtainable from the slopes of these plots. Several conventional ionic surfactants exhibit linear CH plots. The reported^{42,49,51,62} values of β for some of the ionic surfactants in the presence of different salts determined from the CH plots are listed in Table 1. Metallosurfactants have also been reported^{63,64} to exhibit linear CH plots and the examples are *cis*-chlorobis(ethylenediamine)dodecylaminecobalt(III) nitrate⁶³ in aqueous sodium nitrate and *cis*-chlorobis(ethylenediamine)dodecylaminecobalt(III) perchlorate⁶⁴ in aqueous sodium perchlorate. Both these metallosurfactants have $\beta \approx 0.8$.

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Fig. 1. Representative CH plots for SDS, CPC and SDC in aqueous NaCl solution at 25°C (data taken from Refs. 49, 51, 62).

Fig. 2. Representative CH plots for AOT and SDC in aqueous NaCl and Na₂Ox solution at 25°C (data taken from Refs. 48, 62).

Table 1. Counterion binding constant values of different ionic surfactants in the presence of various salts at 25°C

Surfactant	Salt	β	Ref.
Sodium dodecylsulfate	Sodium chloride (^a at 30°C)	0.74	51
		0.71 ^a	42
	Sodium acetate (NaAc)	0.68	51
	Sodium propionate (NaPr)	0.68	51
	Sodium butyrate (NaBu)	0.67	51
Cetylpyridinium chloride	Sodium chloride	0.66	49
	Lithium chloride	0.65	49
	Potassium chloride	0.68	49
Dodecyltrimethylammonium bromide	Sodium bromide (^b at 30°C)	0.48 ^b	42
Sodium deoxycholate	Sodium chloride	0.18	62
	Sodium salicylate (NaSal)	0.10	62

In Fig. 2 a representative CH plot for sodium dioctylsulfosuccinate (AOT)⁴⁸ in the presence of aqueous sodium chloride is shown, which is non-linear unlike the plots for systems presented in Fig. 1. Although the plot is non-linear, the data shown in Fig. 2 were found to fit well into two linear plots. The double-chained anionic surfactant AOT has therefore two β values, a lower value at lower concentration range and a higher value at higher concentration range. Thus, the variation of cmc of AOT with added electrolyte concentration does not strictly obey the CH eq. (2). A similar behaviour of CH plot was found in aqueous SDC system in the presence of sodium oxalate (Na₂Ox)⁶² as shown in Fig. 2. A shift in the slope of the CH plot was also reported for dodecyl-dimethylammonium chloride⁶⁵, for two anionic gemini surfactants^{66,67} and for a double-chained cationic metallosurfactant⁶⁸.

Actually, the size of an ionic micelle increases on adding

electrolyte due to the screening of repulsive interaction between the head groups. In other words, the aggregation number of an ionic micelle increases with increase in electrolyte concentration indicating that the value of β must vary as c_e increases. Empirically the CH plots are found to be linear for several ionic surfactant + salt systems (Fig. 1) showing β to be constant. The linearity of the CH plot observed in a particular range of electrolyte concentrations envisages that in the presence of an added electrolyte both aggregation number and the number of counterions binding to the micelle increase proportionately in such a manner that β remains constant. Non-linearity of CH plot due to disproportionate variations in m and n causing change in β value by the addition of electrolyte was reported in aqueous cetyltrimethylammonium acetate + sodium acetate system⁶⁹. In AOT + NaCl system, the electrolyte concentration at which β switches over from lower to higher value is denoted by c^* . The values of β and c^* are listed in Table 2. From fluorescence quenching studies⁴⁸ it was found that the aggregation number of AOT above c^* suddenly increases from about 40 to 150. Moreover, small-angle neutron scattering (SANS)

Table 2. Counterion binding constant values of AOT and SDC in the presence of salts at 25°C

Salt	c^* (mol kg ⁻¹)	β		Ref.
		Below c^*	Above c^*	
Surfactant: Sodium dioctylsulfosuccinate				
Sodium chloride	0.015	0.39	0.82	48
Sodium acetate		0.37	0.82	
Sodium propionate		0.44	0.80	
Sodium butyrate		0.38	0.85	
Surfactant: Sodium deoxycholate				
Sodium oxalate	0.038	0.05	0.38	62

studies⁵³ revealed that around c^* the shape of AOT micelles undergoes transition from prolate ellipsoidal to rod-like shape. Thus, a sudden shift in the value of β or a change in the slope of the CH plot is indicative of a change in the shape of ionic micelle. The dependence of β on the shape of a micelle was explained in the following manner: As the concentration of added electrolyte increases, the number of counterions bound to a micelle increases thereby reducing the repulsion between the head groups which consequently increases the size or aggregation number of the micelle. However, as the size of the micelle increases, at some point its shape also changes due to geometric requirement so as to accommodate the increased number of hydrocarbon tails in the micelle. Occurrence of such a shape change of the ionic micelle alters the micellar surface area per head group, which upsets the proportionate changes in n and m thereby causing a shift in the value of β . Dependence of β on micelle shape was also reported by Ono *et al.*³¹ for didodecylmethylammonium bromide and by Fujio *et al.*⁷⁰ for dodecylpyridinium bromide and dodecylpyridinium iodide.

Surfactant + salt system with single counterion in water + organic solvent

The nature of the CH plot (having two slopes) of AOT observed in aqueous medium in the presence of NaCl is found to have a dependence on the quality of the solvent. In ethylene glycol (EG) + water medium⁷¹, the CH plot of AOT has two slopes as in the case of water medium when the amount of EG is $\leq 20\%$ (Fig. 3). As the amount of EG becomes more than 20% and less than 40%, the CH plot reverts to normal linear shape with single slope (Table 3). Similar behaviour

Fig. 3. CH plots for AOT + NaCl system in water + ethylene glycol medium at 25°C (data taken from Ref. 71).

Table 3. Counterion binding constant values of AOT in ethylene glycol (EG) + water medium in the presence of sodium chloride at 25°C

Amount of organic solvent	c^* (mol kg ⁻¹)	β		Ref.
		Below c^*	Above c^*	
10% EG	0.010	0.29	0.74	71
20% EG	0.004	0.17	0.57	
30% EG	-	0.44		

was also observed in propylene carbonate (PC) + water medium⁷². The two slopes for the CH plot of AOT existed in 5% PC, but when the amount of PC is 10% or more, the CH plot takes up the normal shape, i.e. a linear plot with single slope. In acetonitrile (AN) + water medium⁷³, the CH plot for AOT exhibited normal shape with single slope even at 5% AN. The two values of β (lower and higher) of AOT as well as the value of c^* decreased as the amount of organic solvent increased, which is attributable to the fact that with increasing amount of organic polar solvent in the medium the hydrophobicity and the dielectric constant decrease thereby reducing the size of the micelles.

When the amount of EG becomes $\geq 40\%$, surprisingly an anomalous type of deviation from the CH plot of AOT occurs⁷¹ as shown in Fig. 4. This anomalous deviation is associated with a reversal in the slope of the CH plot at low concentration region of added electrolyte, viz. the slope of the CH plot tends to become positive instead of the usual negative slope observed at high electrolyte content. This particular deviation was shown to be not due to considering concentration terms instead of activity terms in the CH equation, because even after substituting activity terms in CH equation such anomalous deviation continues to exist⁷¹. The

Fig. 4. Representative CH plots for AOT + NaCl system in water + ethylene glycol medium with EG amount $\geq 40\%$ at 25°C (data taken from Ref. 71).

observed anomalous deviation from the CH equation is attributable to a different type of trend in the variation of $c_0 + c_e$ with c_e in mixed solvent. In mixed solvents or polar organic solvents, the solvophobicity of surfactants is greatly reduced as compared to that in water resulting in high values of cmc for surfactants. On initial addition of electrolyte in to such mixed solvent, drastic decrease in the cmc occurs due to which initially c_0 controls the value of the $c_0 + c_e$ (total concentration of free counterion) term in eq. (2). This trend continues up to a certain electrolyte concentration (c_e^*) and thereafter c_e starts controlling the value of $c_0 + c_e$ term. In other words, the concentration of free counterion in solution is controlled by the ionic surfactant below c_e^* and by the electrolyte above c_e^* . As a result, in mixed solvent containing sufficient polar organic solvent (for e.g. in EG + water medium, when EG amount becomes $\geq 40\%$) the plot of $c_0 + c_e$ versus c_e passes through a minimum at c_e^* ⁷¹. Such a dependence of $c_0 + c_e$ on c_e has not been observed for any surfactant in water. Therefore, if $c_0 + c_e$ does not monotonically increase with increasing c_e in a medium, then in such a medium the CH equation can be used only in the region of electrolyte concentrations lying above c_e^* . It has however been found that the slope of the linear plot in the region of $c_e > c_e^*$ is almost equal to β . Some more examples of systems^{71,74} wherein the above type of anomalous deviation from the CH plot occurs are shown in Fig. 5. In water + EG media, $c_e^* \approx 0.001 \text{ mol kg}^{-1}$ in 40% EG and as the EG amount increases further the value of c_e^* also increases. Thus, it can be inferred that for applying the CH equation there is a lower limit on the concentration of added salt equal to c_e^* . In a mixed

Fig. 5. Representative CH plots for SDS + NaCl (panel A) and AOT + sodium salicylate (NaSal) (panel B) in water + 50% ethylene glycol medium at 25°C (data taken from Refs. 71, 74).

solvent, the value of c_e^* depends on the relative amounts of the two solvents, the nature of solvent and surfactant. In water, c_e^* tends to become zero. From these observations it is estimated that the CH equation is applicable (linear CH plot with negative slope) in a medium if $0 > \partial c_0 / \partial c_e > -1$ ⁷¹.

Aqueous surfactant + salt system with two counterions

If we add an electrolyte having counterion other than that of the ionic surfactant, then we end up with a surfactant + salt system with two or mixed counterions. In such systems the CH equation is not expected to hold good since the CH equation is derived considering the presence of single counterion in a surfactant + salt system. In some surfactant + salt systems containing two counterions^{57,75}, the CH plot is found to be linear or similar to that of the surfactant in the presence of single counterion, which however is an empirical coincidence and does not envisage the validity of CH equation because in these systems the CH equation is not applicable in the true sense. The inapplicability of the CH equation to surfactant + salt system containing two counterions has been demonstrated in Fig. 6A for CPC + sodium salicylate (NaSal)⁵⁵, CPC + sodium benzoate (NaBen)⁵⁵ and cetyltrimethylammonium bromide (CTAB) + NaSal⁷⁶ systems. As expected the plots show deviation from linearity. A modified CH equation for surfactant + salt system with two counterions was therefore derived⁵⁵ as shown below.

The micellization equilibrium between ionic surfactant monomer (cationic surfactant is arbitrarily chosen here) and the two counterions can be represented as

where S and M represent cationic surfactant monomer and ionic micelle with z positive charges, respectively. C_1 is the counterion from the surfactant molecule and C_2 is the added counterion (from the salt). The positive charge on the micelle z is equal to $n - m_1 - m_2$. Using the thermodynamic criterion for the above equilibrium reaction, we get the relation

$$\ln c_s = [(\ln c_m/n) + \Delta G_m^0/(RT)] - (m_1/n) \ln c_1 - (m_2/n) \ln c_2 \quad (4)$$

where c_s , c_m , c_1 and c_2 are concentrations of the surfactant, ionic micelle, counterion 1 and counterion 2, respectively. The equilibrium reaction given above exists when $c_s \geq c_0$. When $c_s > c_0$, $c_1 = c_0 + (c - c_0)(1 - \beta_1)$ and $c_2 = c_e - (c - c_0)\beta_2$.

$\beta_1 = m_1/n$ and $\beta_2 = m_2/n$ represent counterion binding constants of the surfactant for C_1 and C_2 counterions, respectively. The total counterion binding constant (β) of the surfactant is given by $\beta = \beta_1 + \beta_2$. Considering the equilibrium (3) just at the threshold of micellization, i.e. $(c - c_0) \approx 0+$, eq. (4) becomes

$$\ln c_0 = A - B \ln c_e \quad (5)$$

where $A = \Delta G_m^0 / [(1 + \beta_1)RT]$ and $B = \beta_2 / (1 + \beta_1)$. In arriving at eq. (5), the $\ln c_m/n$ term is approximated to be negligible in comparison to $\Delta G_m^0 / RT$. Thus, we get eq. (5) in place of the CH equation for a surfactant system containing two counterions and it is called the modified Corrin-Harkins (MCH) equation⁵⁵. Eq. (5) is applicable only when $c_e > 0$ and the added electrolyte contains counterion different from that in the surfactant molecule. When $c_e = 0$, B also becomes equal to zero and eq. (5) and eq. (2) merge with each other. Whether eq. (5) is a linear equation or not that depends upon the relative values of the two counterion binding constants β_1 and β_2 . In Fig. 6B, MCH plots are shown for the CPC + NaSal, CPC + NaBen and CTAB + NaSal systems and interestingly the plots are linear. The linearity of the MCH plots indicates that in the presence of salicylate + chloride or benzoate + chloride or salicylate + bromide counterions the binding of salicylate or benzoate to the cationic micelle is predominant. Therefore, $\beta_2 \gg \beta_1$ and $1 + \beta_1 \approx 1$ and this must be responsible for making MCH plots linear in Fig. 6B. The relation for β_2 can be written as

$$\beta_2 = B(1 + \beta) / (1 + B) \quad (6)$$

The least-squares fitted values of B are 0.663, 0.659 and 0.568 for CPC + NaSal, CPC + NaBen and CTAB + NaSal

Fig. 6. The CH (panel A) and MCH (panel B) plots for CPC + NaSal, CPC + NaBen and CTAB + NaSal in aqueous medium at 25°C (data taken from Refs. 55, 76).

systems, respectively⁵⁵. The values of β_2 are therefore equal to $0.399(1 + \beta)$, $0.397(1 + \beta)$ and $0.362(1 + \beta)$ for CPC + NaSal, CPC + NaBen and CTAB + NaSal systems, respectively. One disadvantage of the MCH equation is that from its slope the value of β_1 or β_2 or β cannot be obtained directly. Moreover, the MCH plot does not include the data point corresponding to the cmc of surfactant in the absence of electrolyte ($c_e = 0$). The value of the slope B provides the lower limit to β or $\beta \geq B$. For instance, in CPC + NaSal system, if $\beta = 0.8$ (arbitrarily chosen value), $\beta_2 = 0.72$ and $\beta_1 = 0.08$ and in CPC + NaBen system, if $\beta = 0.8$, $\beta_2 = 0.71$ and $\beta_1 = 0.09$. Therefore, the added salicylate or benzoate counterions predominantly bind to the micelle suppressing the binding of chloride ions. This inference is supported by the reported²⁷ higher degree of binding of salicylate than chloride counterions in alkyl trimethylammonium salicylate (C_n TASal, $n = 12, 14, 16$) + NaCl system. Similarly, in CTAB + NaSal system, if $\beta = 0.8$, $\beta_2 = 0.65$ and $\beta_1 = 0.15$. Higher value of β_1 for bromide than chloride is in accordance with the known fact that bromide counterions bind to ionic micelles more than chloride counterions which is supported by the positions of these two ions in the Hofmeister series⁷⁷. In CPC + phenol red (sodium salt) system also it has been reported⁷⁸ that the CH plot is non-linear due to the presence of two counterions and on using MCH equation the plots become linear.

The CH and MCH plots for aqueous AOT + tetrapropylammonium bromide (TPAB) and AOT + tetrabutylammonium bromide (TBAB) systems⁵⁷ are shown in Fig. 7. From Fig. 7 it may be noticed that the MCH plot for each system

Fig. 7. The CH (panel A) and MCH (panel B) plots for AOT + TPAB and AOT + TBAB in aqueous medium at 25°C (data taken from Ref. 57).

consists of two straight lines instead of one single line. The nature of these MCH plots is similar to that of the CH plot of aqueous AOT + NaCl system shown above in Fig. 2. It has been confirmed by SANS study⁵⁷ that the switch over in the slope of the MCH plot of AOT + TPAB or AOT + TBAB system is associated with a transition from micelle to vesicle. Thus a sudden shift in the slope of either CH or MCH plot is indicative of a transition in the morphology of microstructures of ionic surfactant + salt systems.

Ionic surfactant + salt systems containing mixed counterions are important as they may be treated as model systems to investigate the specific ion effect. On the basis of the competitive binding of two counterions to micellar surface the selectivity coefficient for the two ions can be estimated and this selectivity coefficient serves as a parameter for quantifying specific ion effect. It has been reported⁷⁹ that in a surfactant + salt system containing mixed counterions if the MCH plot is non-linear then it is possible to estimate the selectivity coefficients for the two counterions, which signifies an important application of eq. (5). The method of estimation of selectivity coefficient is demonstrated by considering aqueous CPC + NaAc system⁷⁹. The MCH plot for this system is shown in Fig. 8 and it is a non-linear plot. In this system, there is a competition between chloride and acetate ions to bind to the micellar surface and by applying the pseudo-ion-exchange model⁸⁰, the ion exchange equilibrium is given by

where the ions in the solution (free ions) and the ions bound to the micelle are indicated by the subscripts s and b, respectively. The expression for the equilibrium constant K_e of the above ion exchange equilibrium is

$$K_e = (\beta_2[c_s - (c_s - c_0)\beta_1]) / (\beta_1[c_e - (c_s - c_0)\beta_2]) \quad (8)$$

Near the cmc, eq. (8) takes the form

$$K_e = (c_0\beta_2) / (\beta_1c_e) \quad (9)$$

The ratio of counterion binding constants β_1/β_2 is therefore proportional to the ratio c_0/c_e . After substituting for β_1 from eq. (9) in the expression for $B = \beta_2/(1 + \beta_1)$, we get

$$B = (\beta_2K_e c_e) / (K_e c_e + c_0\beta_2) \quad (10)$$

Eq. (10) envisages that B is dependent on c_e and thus exchange of counterions at the micellar interface accounts for the non-linear dependence of $\ln c_0$ on $\ln c_e$. Eq. (10) may be rewritten as

$$1/\beta_2 = (1/B) - [c_0/(K_e c_e)] \quad (11)$$

At high values of c_e , the second term on the right hand side of eq. (11) may become less significant compared to $1/B$ and in such region of salt concentrations $\beta_2 \approx B$ and $\beta_1 \approx 0$. In fact, above 4.7 mmol kg^{-1} NaAc (this concentration limit is denoted by $c^\#$) the plot of $\ln c_0$ versus $\ln c_e$ showed very good linearity (Fig. 8) and the corresponding B value obtained from the least-squares fitting is 0.68. It is interesting to find that this value of $B = \beta_2 = \beta$ (because $\beta_1 \approx 0$ in this region) is comparable to the reported^{15,49} values of β for CPC and CPAC.

Fig. 8. The MCH plot for CPC + NaAc system in aqueous medium at 25°C (data taken from Ref. 79).

For determining the value of K_e in the salt concentration region below $c^\#$, the $\ln c_0$ versus $\ln c_e$ data in this region were fitted to a polynomial and using the fitted coefficients of the polynomial the values of the slope B were calculated as $\partial \ln c_0 / \partial \ln c_e$. Then the value of K_e was adjusted by iteration such that the values of β_1 and β_2 calculated using the relation $\beta_1 = B/(y - B)$ and $\beta_2 = \beta_1 y$, where $y = c_e K_e / c_0$, give the

acceptable value for the total counterion binding constant β (≈ 0.7). In the salt concentration region above $c^\#$, the constant value of B equal to the slope of the linear plot of $\ln c_0$ versus $\ln c_e$ was used to estimate K_e . The value of K_e obtained thus in the complete experimental concentration region (below and above $c^\#$) is found to be 0.5 ± 0.1 (this K_e is denoted by $K_{Ac/Cl}$). Abuin *et al.*⁴ and Lissi *et al.*⁵ determined by using absorption and fluorescence spectroscopy the selectivity coefficients for the exchange of acetate and bromide ions ($K_{Ac/Br} = 0.05$) and also for the exchange of bromide and chloride ions ($K_{Br/Cl} = 5.0$). From these two selectivity coefficients $K_{Ac/Cl}$ is calculated using the relation $K_{ZY} = K_{XY}/K_{XZ}$ and $K_{YZ} = 1/K_{ZY}$ and it was found that $K_{Ac/Cl} \approx 0.3$, which is fairly in good agreement with the value estimated from the MCH plot. Thus, the above approach for calculating K_e on the basis of the MCH equation can be employed as a new method for determining selectivity coefficients.

Concluding remarks

In aqueous ionic surfactant + salt systems containing single counterion, the CH equation provides a convenient experimental method to determine the counterion binding constant. In these systems, the CH plots exhibit linearity only if the added salt does not induce shape change of the micelle. Therefore, CH plots are linear in the region of salt concentration where shape of ionic micelle remains unchanged. A shift in the slope of CH plot serves as an indicator of micellar shape change. At high concentrations of salt, even if the salt does not induce micellar shape change, the CH plot deviates from linearity due to salting-out effect. In water + polar organic solvent medium, when the organic solvent amount exceeds 40% the CH plot deviates from linearity at low salt concentrations and even tends to exhibit positive slope. In such a medium, slope of the CH plot corresponding to higher salt concentration region (excluding the region where CH plot has positive slope) however provides almost correct value of the counterion binding constant. In aqueous ionic surfactant + salt system containing two counterions, the CH equation takes a modified form. The plot of the modified CH equation is linear if one of the counterions predominantly binds to the micelle. A switch over in the slope of the modified CH plot also indicates occurrence of micellar shape change. If the

modified CH plot is non-linear, the variable slope values can be used to determine (by iterative data fitting) the selectivity coefficient for the exchange of two counterions at the micellar surface.

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